

JANUARY 12, 2023

ATLAS OF VARIANT EFFECTS ALLIANCE

2022 ANNUAL REPORT

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INTRODUCTION

The Atlas of Variant Effects (AVE) Alliance is an international collaborative founded in 2020 whose efforts are focused on developing, disseminating and democratizing the foundational experimental and analytical technologies for mapping variant effects. We want to thank everyone for their hard work and input in 2022! We know that leads and members of our workstreams and committees have contributed countless hours collectively working on crafting strategic roadmaps, building resources, publishing reviews, all of which is progress towards our shared vision of building an Atlas of Variant Effects. We also are thankful for all of our event presenters, our event planning committee members, and to sponsors for their financial support of our annual symposium. We're excited to share with you this annual report highlighting Alliance activities in 2022.

OBJECTIVES OF THE ALLIANCE

1. Bring together data generators, curators and consumers, along with funders and other stakeholders from across the globe to set standards, share tools and develop strategy.
2. Facilitate production of a collection of comprehensive variant effect maps (a nucleotide-resolution atlas) that could ultimately assist in the diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment of disease.
3. Create community-driven, democratic resources for sharing, discovering and analyzing large-scale variant effect data.

OUR VALUES AND PRINCIPLES

- Inclusivity
- Open Access Science
- Research Excellence and Integrity
- Respect, Relevance, Reciprocity, Responsibility, Relationships

TIMELINE

2022

- Workstream roadmaps publicly available on website (Dec 2022)
- Variant Effect Seminar Series (VESS) 1 yr anniversary (Sept 2022)
- 5th Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium (Jun 2022)
- Membership milestone: 400th member, over 20 countries (Aug 2022)
- Membership milestone: 300th member, over 15 countries (Feb 2022)

2021

- AVE Twitter account created (Oct 2021)
- Workstream Roadmap Drafts circulated for Internal Review (Oct 2021)
- Early career scientist led Variant Effect Seminar Series (VESS) launched (Sept 2021)
- Membership milestone: 200 from over 10 countries (July 2021)
- Outreach Diversity and Inclusion Committee formed (June 2021)
- Strategic Plan made publicly available (Apr 2021)
- Workstreams formed (Feb 2021)

2020

- AVE Officially launched (Oct 2020)
- AVE Website created (Aug 2020)
- AVE Slack channel created (July 2020)
- First Conceived (Jan 2020)

HIGHLIGHTS FROM 2022

- Executive Committee strategic refresh planning (Fall 2022)
- Perspective paper outlining the vision for an Atlas of Variant Effects (planned submission to Genome Biology Feb 2023)
- Call for papers as part of a Special Collection in Genome Biology (focused on multiplex assays of variant effect)
- Open call for new members in workstreams (adding 10 new members and bringing in new co-leads for the ETS and AMP workstreams)
- Monthly early career scientist-led Variant Effects Seminar Series (VESS) (22 speakers in 2021, videos freely available on YouTube)
- Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium (MSS) (5th annual 2022 (Hybrid) held June 13-16th at the University of Toronto, Canada)
- Launch of a new educational resources page on our website

MEMBERS

Executive Committee: David Adams, Fritz Roth, Anna Gloyn, Matthew Hurles, Doug Fowler, Debbie Marks, JT Neal, Alan Rubin, Lea Starita

Admin and Project management support: Alex Hopkins and Lara Muffley

Outreach Diversity and Inclusion Committee co-leads: Willow Coyote-Maestas and Irene Gallego Romero

Workstream co-leads: Melina Claussnitzer (ETS), Victoria Nicole Parikh (ETS), Debbie Marks (AMP), Ben Lehner (AMP), Alan Rubin (DCD), Lea Starita (CVI), Clare Turnbull (CVI).

VESS Planning Committee: Diego Calderon, Steven Erwood, Mireia Seuma, Yann Ilboudo, Adrine de Souza

Alliance Members : We currently have over 400 members from the following 30 countries: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, China, Denmark, Ecuador, Estonia, France, Germany, India, Iran, Italy, Japan, Luxembourg, Malaysia, Mexico, Netherlands, New Zealand, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Singapore, South Africa, Republic of Korea, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom, and the United States.

WORKSTREAM PROGRESS

Four Working Groups were established in 2021 to help realize the goals of the Alliance:

1. [Experimental Technology and Standards \(ETS\)](#)
2. [Analysis, Modelling and Prediction \(AMP\)](#)
3. [Clinical Variant Interpretation \(CVI\)](#)
4. [Data Coordination and Dissemination \(DCD\)](#)

4 Interconnected Work streams

All 4 workstreams added new members in 2022 and have been meeting monthly and working asynchronously. Workstream Roadmaps are now also publicly available on our website <https://www.varianteffect.org/workstreams>. Each workstream presented a short progress summary at the 2022 Mutational Scanning Symposium, and the [video can be viewed on our youtube site](#). Below is a summary of what was presented along with updates.

The **Experimental Technology and Standards (ETS) workstream** led by Melina Claussnitzer and Victoria Nicole Parikh, facilitates the development, scaling, evaluation, comparison and dissemination of new MAVE methods. They are actively working to:

- Establish a controlled vocabulary for describing variant effect mapping methods
- Develop strategies to guide others' experimental design
- Outline the content of an information resource for alternative technologies with protocols, design principles, controls, tips, caveats

MAVE resources and tools

Multiplexed assays of variant effects (MAVEs) allow us to assess (in a single experiment) thousands of variants simultaneously. This technique which harnesses the power of next-gen sequencing yields large-scale data sets that can shed light on the functional consequences of protein variants and ultimately on the the landscape of human genetic variation.

Note: We are currently working on providing a comprehensive MAVE knowledge base

This page is under construction - but we hope these preliminary links will be a helpful starting place

If you are interested in helping to develop this resource please contact project manager Lara Muffley (muffley@u.w.edu)

MaveDB
A public repository for variant effect maps

MaveVis
A visualization tool for variant effect maps in MaveDB

MAVE impute
Impute missing data for variant effect maps

MAVE registry
A collaborative resource for sharing progress on MAVEs

Amazing MAVE projects TRACKED HERE
MAVE Registry is a collaborative resource for sharing progress on Multiplexed Assays of Variant Effect (MAVE).
[Browse Projects](#) [Nominate Targets](#)

Educational Resources

Comprehensive MAVE-relevant reviews (MAVE Experimental Design and Technology Standards) Thinking about incorporating MAVEs into your work? Here are useful comprehensive reviews:

[Tabet D, Parikh V, Meil P, Roth F.P. & Claussnitzer M. Scalable functional assays for the interpretation of human genetic variation. Annu Rev Genet. 2022.](#)

[Geck B.C., Boyle G, Amorosi C.J., Fowler D.M. & Dunham M.J. Measuring pharmacogenetic variant function at scale using multiplexed assays. Annu Rev Pharmacol Toxicol. 2022.](#)

[Finlay G.M. Linking genome variants to disease: scalable approaches to test the functional impact of human mutations. Hum Mol Genet. 2021.](#)

[Kinney J.B. & McCandlish D.M. Massively parallel assays and quantitative sequence-function relationships. Annu Rev Genom Hum Genet. 2019.](#)

[Welle J. & Roth F.P. Multiplexed assays of variant effects contribute to a growing genotype-phenotype atlas. Hum Genet. 2018.](#)

[Starita L.M., Ahluw N, Dunham M.J., Kitzman J.O., Roth F.P., Seelig O., Shendure J. & Fowler D.M. Variant interpretation: functional assays to the rescue. Am J Hum Genet. 2017.](#)

[Gasparini M, Starita L & Shendure J. The power of multiplexed functional assays of genetic variants. Nat Protoc. 2016.](#)

Technology and methods development manuscripts Designing a MAVE? >>Follow [this link](#)<< to view granular reviews and seminal papers relevant to methods at each stage of the MAVE development process

Are we missing something?
If there is a critical review, stage or category of MAVE experimental design or technology that you think should be included here, please tell us at this link: [Google Sheet](#)

We will review and incorporate your suggestions at our experimental and technology standards (ETS) workstream meetings monthly.

The ETS workstream has built out content for the MAVE Educational Resource page. In particular the Educational Resources section which includes a list of comprehensive MAVE relevant review articles and technology and methods manuscripts.

Annual Review of Genetics

Scalable Functional Assays for the Interpretation of Human Genetic Variation

Daniel Tabet,^{1,2} Victoria Parikh,³ Prashant Mali,⁴ Frederick P. Roth,^{1,2} and Melina Claussnitzer^{5,6,7}

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Keywords

functional assays, genetic variation, variant effect mapping, sequence–function studies, multiplexed assays of variant effect

Abstract

Scalable sequence–function studies have enabled the systematic study and cataloging of hundreds of thousands of coding and noncoding genetic variants in the human genome. This has improved clinical variant interpretation and provided insights into the molecular, biophysical, and cellular effects of genetic variants at an astonishing scale and resolution across the spectrum of allele frequencies. In this review, we explore current applications and prospects for the field, and outline the principles underlying scalable functional assay design, with a focus on the study of single-nucleotide coding and noncoding variants.

This year, members of the ETS workstream also published a Review Article on ‘Scalable Functional Assays for the Interpretation of Human Genetic Variation’.

The **Analysis, Modelling and Prediction (AMP) workstream** is led by Debbie Marks and Ben Lehner. The AMP workstream's mission is to promote the development of computational tools and standards. They are working on:

- Benchmarking datasets (for input into MAVEDB w/ expert annotation)
- Prediction and Evaluation metrics (review paper on tools, metrics, and upcoming CAGI competitions)
- Experimental design recommendations (including gene prioritization)

The **Data Coordination and Dissemination (DCD)** workstream led by Alan Rubin facilitates the distribution of MAVE data primarily by overseeing the growth and management of a MAVE database. This team is currently working on:

- Building on previous work to define Minimum Information Standards for MAVES
- Creating protocols for annotating and mapping MAVE datasets
- Mapping MAVE datasets to reference genomes and reference transcripts
- Capturing the genetic backgrounds used for MAVES
- Developing Data models for individual MAVE variants
- Models for clinical variant interpretation
- Models for ML/prediction applications
- Defining Data quality metrics for MAVES
- Ensuring that MAVES adhere to FAIR/CARE data principles

The **Outreach Diversity and Inclusion Committee (ODIC)** led by Willow Coyote-Maestas and Irene Gallego Romero, has parallel inward and outward facing missions to 1) increase the diversity and inclusion within AVE 2) Facilitate partnerships between the Alliance and stakeholder communities 3) Explore ethical and equitable MAVE design, execution and dissemination. This committee is actively working on:

- Exploring how MAVE/MPRA/DMS can shed light on genotype-phenotype relationships in populations under-represented within clinical genetic databases
- Spearheading conversations about the ethical and social impacts of MAVES
- Give ELSI speakers a platform in AVE

MUTATIONAL SCANNING SYMPOSIUM

Each year, the Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance hosts the Mutational Scanning Symposium where experts in the fields of functional genomics, protein science, precision medicine, variant interpretation, and computational genetics come from around the world to connect, present their work, discuss new methods and provide insights into the future of this science.

The 5th annual Mutational Scanning Symposium was held in Toronto, Canada (and online) June 13th, 14th and 16th, 2022. There were 133 in-person attendees in Toronto plus another 229 participating virtually in real time, all from 20 countries. This year, the three day program included keynote lectures by Clare Turnbull and Doug Fowler, as well as 25 invited talks and 10 lightning talks selected from poster abstracts. We also held a virtual poster session using GatherTown that attracted 86 posters. Topics ranged from technology, to clinical variant interpretation, to sequence/structure/function relationships, to variation and evolution. Most speakers agreed to help us create a community resource by making their talks permanently available on [YouTube](#).

In 2023, the [Symposium](#) will be at the Wellcome Sanger Institute July 13th - 14th in the UK and online.

Group photo from the 5th Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium, Toronto, Canada.

Graphic summary highlights from the 5th Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium.

VARIANT EFFECTS SEMINAR SERIES (VESS)

In this series, early-career scientists from around the globe share and discuss their research related to interpreting human genetic variation. In September, VESS celebrated its one year anniversary and in October, two new members joined the organizing committee, Yann Ilboudo (McGill University) and Adrine de Souza (University of Toronto).

Examples of recent VESS videos posted on Youtube page.

Announcements about upcoming seminars on AVE Twitter

NEWSWORTHY

In May, our Clinical Variant Interpretation workstream co-chairs Clare Turnbull and Lea Starita were guests on the GA4GH OmicsXchange podcast where they discussed

interpreting human genetic variation and the Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance (<https://www.ga4gh.org/news/omicsxchange-episode-16-atlas-variant-effects-alliance-and-interpreting-human-genetic-variation-with-clare-turnbull-and-lea-starita/>)

“As a user of these data rather than a generator of them, I can only speak to how transformative it was when Lea and colleagues published what was one of the first MAVE publications. And suddenly, we had reliable functional data on nearly every possible substitution that could arise in the key regions of BRCA1. This completely rocked our world in terms of how we classified variants in this gene.” Clare Turnbull excerpt from GA4GH OmicsXchange podcast

"WITH LESS THAN THREE YEARS OF ADDITIONAL DATA, WE MORE THAN DOUBLED THE NUMBER OF HUMAN DMS DATASETS IN THIS ANALYSIS, AND IT IS LIKELY THAT WITH PROJECTS LIKE THE ATLAS OF VARIANT EFFECTS (WWW.VARIANTEFFECT.ORG), THE AVAILABILITY OF SUCH DATASETS, AND THEIR UTILITY FOR PROTEIN VARIANT INTERPRETATION, WILL EXPLODE." - LIVESEY & MARSH

In November, AMP workstream member Joseph A. Marsh and colleague Benjamin J. Livesey, published the preprint ["Updated benchmarking of variant effect predictors using deep mutational scanning"](#). An excerpt from the paper highlights the important work of the Alliance.

CROSS CONSORTIA COLLABORATIONS

In July of 2022, AVE Executive committee members met with NHGRI to discuss how to build on existing collaborations between AVE, ClinGen, GREGoR and IGVF. Topics included:

- Approaches to prioritization of genes/variants
- Centralizing relevant information across programs
- Variant scope (i.e. protein coding, non-coding, and regulatory)
- Information on variant effects, function, etc. that would be most useful across all resources
- Standards for data exchange/interoperability (including existing GA4GH, AVE, and ClinGen standards)

GOALS FOR 2023

The AVE executive committee held a series of strategic refresh planning meetings in the fall of 2022. The full report summary can be found [HERE](#). In brief, Alliance activities will be focused on the following priorities over the next 2-3 years:

SUSTAINMENT

- Continue to host and support the Mutational Scanning Symposium and the Variant Effects Seminar Series
- Continue to diversify and expand our membership
- Continue to deliver on the strategic objectives of the four core workstreams

COMPLETION of ONGOING INITIATIVES

- Support workstreams in completing projects outlined in their roadmaps (i.e standards papers)
- Support members of AVE generating variant effect maps by providing educational resources

GROWTH

- Increase the number of groups generating variant effect maps and sharing data in public repositories
- Track key metrics of success
- Ensure the financial sustainability of the Alliance (and of key infrastructure like MaveDB)
- Lead and secure funding for operations (AVE administrative staff, programmatic and resource sustainment) and 2 new large scale data generational flagship projects

OPPORTUNITIES TO ENGAGE AND CONNECT

There are multiple ways to get involved with the Alliance or learn about mutational scanning here are a few options:

- Join the Alliance (<https://www.varianteffect.org/membership>)
- Participate and/or present at the monthly [Variant Effects Seminar Series](#) (VESS)
- Participate and/or present at the [Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium](#)
- Join a workstream or committee! Workstreams open membership on an ad-hoc basis. Open calls can be found under the membership tab on our [website](#).
- Watch Educational Videos on our [YouTube channel](#) (co-managed with [CMAP](#))

- Register your project on [MaveRegistry](#)
- Deposit your variant effect maps in [MaveDB](#)
- Members of the Alliance can join AVE Slack and post in one of the open channels:
 - ❖ #education
 - ❖ #general
 - ❖ #introductions
 - ❖ #job_announcements
 - ❖ #literature
 - ❖ #random
 - ❖ #tips-tricks-troubleshooting
 - ❖ #variant-effects-seminar-series

“The AVE Alliance represents a next step in, and will help drive, the adoption and impact of mutational scanning. As the Alliance has grown, I’ve been so happy that the community is so collegial, inclusive, and collaborative. The takeaway is just how versatile mutational scanning is to answer all sorts of questions in biology, protein engineering, and medicine.” - Doug Fowler

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